

The Ionic Susceptibilities of Rubidium from its Different Salts in the Solid and in the Dissolved State.

BY S. S. BHATNAGAR, M. B. NEVGI AND MOHAN LAL KHANNA.

The ionic susceptibilities for rubidium obtained by different authors* are not consistent. The theoretical values obtained by Pauling, Stoner, Slater, and Angus are 35.0, 30.12, 25.8 and 24.05 respectively, while those obtained experimentally by Pascal, Kido, Ikenmeyer and Abonnenc are 27.2, 27.2, 31.3 and 25.0. (The values refer to $-\chi \times 10^6$). The present investigation has been undertaken to investigate into the causes of these discrepancies which may be ascertained from a knowledge of the values of χ for the rubidium ion from its salts in the solid and dissolved state and the influence of temperature on them. The susceptibilities under different conditions are also capable of yielding information regarding the sizes of molecular diameters and use has been made of the data in settling the well known controversy between the various authors as to whether or not the radii of the rubidium ion in the solid and the dissolved state are different. There have been many contributions to the subject, both theoretical and practical. For example, Joos, Ikenmeyer, Reicheneder and Weiss have determined the ionic diamagnetic values of K, Cl, Cs, I, halogens and H ions. Hecart, Farquharson, Kido and Scott and Blair have also made notable contributions in this domain.†

The general expression for the diamagnetic susceptibility of a symmetrical atom or ion, which is due to Langevin (*Ann. chim. Phys.*, 1905, 5, 70), is

* Pauling (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1927, A, 114, 181); Stoner (*Proc. Leeds Phil. Soc.*, 1929, 1, 484); Slater (*Phys. Rev.*, 1930, 36, 58); Angus (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1932, A, 136, 569); Pascal (*Compt. rend.*, 1913, 156, 323; 1915, 158, 37); Kido, (*Sci. Rep. Tohoku Imp. Univ.*, 1932, 21, 149; 1933, 22, 235); Ikenmeyer (*Ann. Phys.*, 1929, 1, 169); Abonnenc, (*Compt. rend.*, 1934, 198, 2237).

† Joos (*Z. Physik*, 1923, 19, 347; 1925, 23, 835); Ikenmeyer. (*loc. cit.*); Reicheneder. (*Ann. Physik*, 1929, 3, 59); Weiss, (*J. Phys.*, 1930, 1, 185; *Compt. rend.*, 1930, 190, 95); Hocart (*Compt. rend.*, 1929, 188, 1151); Farquharson, (*Phil. Mag.*, 1931, 12, 283); Kido, (*loc. cit.*); Scott and Blair, (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1933, 35, 475).

$$\chi = -\frac{Ne^2}{6mc^2} \sum_n \bar{r}^2$$

where \bar{r} is the average distance of the electron from the nucleus or the time average value. The result is not modified except in respect of the different treatment of electron position co-ordinates such as \bar{r} . Van Vleck (*Phys. Rev.*, 1928, **31**, 587) and Pauling (*loc. cit.*) have independently calculated the value of \bar{r} . An extension of Pauling's work has been made by Gray and his collaborators (*Phil. Mag.*, 1930, **10**, 191; 1931, **11**, 81). Using Hartree's space-charge distribution method (*Proc. Camb. Phil. Soc.*, 1928, **24**, 89), Stoner (*loc. cit.*) has deduced a number of ionic susceptibilities. However, the theoretical values obtained so far are much higher than those obtained experimentally. Zener (*Phys. Rev.*, 1930, **36**, 57) has shown that the nodes in a wave function are unimportant. Slater (*loc. cit.*) has made use of this and calculated the mean square radius of the inert gases. Brindley (*Phil. Mag.*, 1931, **11**, 786) has shown that the ionic susceptibilities calculated according to the Slater's formula are in better agreement with the experimental results than those of Pauling or Stoner (*loc. cit.*). Recently Angus (*loc. cit.*) has modified the Slater's formula and found that it gives values which are in good agreement with the experimental results.

A comparative study of the whole subject, particularly with a view to settle the controversy mentioned above, has been undertaken in this investigation,

EXPERIMENTAL.

The apparatus employed during this investigation is a modified form of Decker's balance (Bhatnagar, Nevgi and Tuli, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1935, **9**, 311). In order to determine the susceptibilities at different temperatures, the portion of the tube between the upper stop-cock and the glass window is double-jacketted with an inlet and outlet for the circulation of water at different temperatures. The lower end of the tube carries two stop-cocks between which is fused a side-tube which serves the purpose of introducing the liquid under investigation. Sufficient care was taken to prevent the pole-pieces from getting heated. However, it is just likely that the ends of the pole-pieces might be absorbing some heat and thereby the field might be decreased to some extent. In order to do away with this source of error,

readings with the standard substances, *i.e.*, water and air, were taken separately at the two temperatures for calculating the values of the specific susceptibility at two different temperatures. In order to ensure that the liquid to be investigated has attained the temperature of hot water circulating round it, water was allowed to circulate for a sufficiently long time before taking the readings. In order to be more sure about it, the susceptibilities of copper sulphate and copper chloride solutions were determined at two different temperatures and therefrom the value of the higher temperature was calculated.

TABLE I.

Substance.	Temperature	
	Calc.	Obs.
Copper sulphate	59.5°	60°
Copper chloride	59.7°	60°

The agreement between the observed and the calculated values clearly shows that the solution in the tube always acquires the temperature of the circulating water. The specific susceptibility in the dissolved state has been calculated according to the following equation (*cf.* Bhatnagar, Nevgi and Tuli, *loc. cit.*):

$$\chi_i = \frac{\phi_i \left[\frac{\chi_w - \chi_a}{\phi_w - \phi_a} \right] + \left[\frac{\chi_a \phi_w - \chi_w \phi_a}{\phi_w - \phi_a} \right]}{d}$$

where χ_i denotes mass susceptibility of the solution, χ_a , that of the air, χ_w , that of the water; ϕ_i , angle of torsion due to the solution, ϕ_a , that one to air, ϕ_w , due to water, d , the density of the solution.

The specific susceptibility of the salt from that of the solution has been calculated with the help of the relation:

$$\chi_i = \chi_{\text{salt}} \times C_{\text{salt}} + \chi_{\text{solvent}} (1 - C_{\text{salt}}).$$

where C_{salt} denotes the concentration of the salt in solution.

The specific susceptibility of the salts in the solid state has been determined by a suitably modified form of Guoy's balance.

The apparatus consisted of a very sensitive weighing balance on a hollow wooden box. The left pan of the balance was replaced by a half pan similar to the one generally used in the specific gravity determination of lighter bodies. To the bottom of this pan was soldered a hollow cylinder which carried a movable hook carrying a fine glass suspension. By means of the hook, the suspension could be raised up or lowered down. Just below the hook, there is a small hole in the base of the balance through which a fine glass thread two feet in length passes. The lower end of the glass thread has a stirrup-like arrangement, while its upper end is attached to the hook and fixed with the help of the sealing wax. The portion of the suspension fibre between the base of the balance and the box is protected from disturbances due to the air-draughts by inserting a glass tube of 3" in diameter.

The sample tube consists of two tubes A and B; the latter acts as a stopper to the former. B is sealed and contains the paramagnetic substance. The tube is made to hang in the glass stirrup by means of two fine glass fibres R and R', projected at the top of the tube. In order to keep the tube B in the same position with respect to A, the projected fibre P' in the sealed tube B is always made to coincide with the projected fibre R' of the tube A. Secondly in order to keep the whole system in the same position with respect to the magnet, a small mirror is placed behind the tube. In front of this mirror a thin wire-gauze is placed (A mark P is made in the tube A.). By means of the parallax method, the tube is placed in the same position every time. The lower end of the specimen tube comes in between the poles of the big electromagnet as shown in the figure. At first the pull due to the paramagnetic substance only is noted and then the combined pull due to para as well as diamagnetic substances together is read (care being taken that the combined pull should be of attraction). By subtracting the combined pull from that due to the paramagnetic substance only, one can easily find out the repulsion due to the diamagnetic substances.

The force acting on the cylinder along its axis is given by

$$F_x = (\chi_1 m_1 - \chi_2 m_2) H_y \frac{\partial H_y}{\partial x} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

where χ_1 and χ_2 are the mass susceptibilities of the substance and the medium and m_1 and m_2 are the masses of the specimen and the medium occupying the same volume as the specimen respectively. If W_g is the pull due to the empty tube only, then

$$W_g = (\chi_g m_g - \chi_a m_{a.g}) H_y \frac{\partial H_y}{\partial x} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

where χ_g denotes the mass susceptibility of the glass tube, χ_a that of the medium, m_g and $m_{a.g}$ are the mass of the glass tube and of the medium displaced by the glass tube. If W_p is the additional pull due to the paramagnetic substance, then

$$W_g + W_p = \left[(\chi_p m_p + \chi_g m_g) - \chi_a (m_{a.g} + m_{a.p}) \right] H_y \frac{\partial H_y}{\partial x} \quad \dots \quad (iii)$$

where χ_p denotes mass susceptibility of the paramagnetic substance, m_p , mass of the paramagnetic substance, $m_{a.p}$, mass of the medium displaced by the paramagnetic substance.

If W_{d_1} is the pull due to the diamagnetic substance then

$$W_g + W_p + W_{d_1} = \left[(\chi_g m_g + \chi_p m_p + \chi_{d_1} m_{d_1}) - \chi_a (m_{a.g} + m_{a.p} + m_{a.d_1}) \right] H_y \frac{\partial H_y}{\partial x} \quad \dots \quad (iv)$$

Subtracting (iii) from (iv) it gives :

$$W_{d_1} = \left(\chi_{d_1} m_{d_1} - \chi_a m_{a.d_1} \right) H_y \frac{\partial H_y}{\partial x} \quad \dots \quad (v)$$

Similarly the pull due to some other diamagnetic substance d_2 can be found out and

$$W_{d_2} = \left(\chi_{d_2} m_{d_2} - \chi_a m_{a.d_2} \right) H_y \frac{\partial H_y}{\partial x} \quad \dots \quad (vi)$$

Dividing (v) by (vi)

$$\frac{W_{d_1}}{W_{d_2}} = \frac{\chi_{d_1} m_{d_1} - \chi_a m_{a \cdot d_1}}{\chi_{d_2} m_{d_2} - \chi_a m_{a \cdot d_2}}$$

$$\therefore x_{d_2} = \frac{1}{m_{d_2}} \left[\left(\chi_{d_1} m_{d_1} - \chi_a m_{a \cdot d_1} \right) \frac{W_{d_2}}{W_{d_1}} + \chi_a m_{a \cdot d_2} \right] \quad (vii)$$

This equation has been used for calculating the susceptibilities of the substances under investigation.

The calculations given above hold when both the substances are in the inhomogeneous field; but even if part of the tube containing the paramagnetic material is in the inhomogeneous and the diamagnetic in the homogeneous field, the final formula will hold as the method is a purely substituted one and is independent of the field gradient.

For higher temperature measurements, an electric oven made of mica pieces and nichrom wire was used. In order to avoid the changes in the field that might perhaps be produced near the pole pieces, the readings for the standard substances were repeated at higher temperatures and were found to be the same as those at the lower temperatures. In order to see whether the substances in the tube had attained the temperature recorded by the thermometer in the electric furnace, anhydrous copper sulphate and cobalt sulphate were tried and from the Curie-Weiss law,

$$\chi_M = \frac{C_M}{T - \theta}$$

the values of temperature were calculated.

TABLE II.

Substance.	Temperature.	
	Calc.	Obs.
Copper sulphate (anhydrous)	89.4°	90°
Cobalt sulphate (anhydrous)	89.6°	90°

The agreement between the observed and the calculated values of temperatures justifies the above assumption.

As the purity of the substances employed is of great importance, Merck's extra pure rubidium salts were used during this investigation. The results are shown in the tables below.

TABLE III.

Salt.	$-\chi \times 10^6$ at 30° solid.	$-\chi \times 10^6$ at 20° solution.	$-\chi \times 10^6$ ionic (solid).	$-\chi \times 10^6$ ionic (solution).
RbCl	0.386	0.386	26.45	26.68
RbBr	0.346	0.347	26.63	26.78
RbI	0.336	0.337	26.76	26.97
Rb ₂ SO ₄	0.331	0.331	27.38	27.38

TABLE IV.

Temperature effect.

Salt.	Solid			Solution	
	$-\chi \times 10^6$ at 30°.	$-\chi \times 10^6$ at 60°.	$-\chi \times 10^6$ at 20°.	$-\chi \times 10^6$ at 60°.	$-\chi \times 10^6$ at 60°.
RbCl	0.385	0.390	0.386		0.395
RbBr	0.346	0.350	0.347		0.351
RbI	0.336	0.340	0.337		0.345
Rb ₂ SO ₄	0.331	0.335	0.331		0.336

DISCUSSION.

Many interesting points arise out of the results described in this paper. The general expression for the ionic susceptibility is

$$\chi_{\text{ion}} = -\frac{N e^2}{6m e^2} \sum_n \bar{r}^2 = 2.832 \times 10^{10} \sum \bar{r}^2$$

If in this expression the value of χ_{ion} for rubidium is substituted, the ionic value for radius of the rubidium ion can be easily calculated and is equal to 1.875×10^{-8} cm. Scott (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931,

35, 1410), Pauling (*loc. cit.*), Goldsmidh (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1929, 25, 282) and Webb (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 2589) have obtained the ionic radius of rubidium from the different states of rubidium salts. The values obtained by them are given in Table V.

TABLE V

Ionic radius of rubidium.

Author.	State.	Ionic value.
Scott	Saturated solution	1.37×10^{-8} cm.
Pauling	Theoretical, crystalline state	1.48×10^{-8}
Goldsmidh	Empirical, crystalline state	1.49×10^{-8}
Webb	Dilute solutions	2.02×10^{-8}
Present authors.	Solid as well as dissolved state	1.875×10^{-8}

The value 1.875×10^{-8} cm obtained is approximately mid-way between the two sets of values given above.

The ionic diamagnetism of rubidium ion is the same in the solid as well as in the dissolved state. It is obvious that if the numerical value of χ_{ion} remains the same in the equation given above, the ionic value for the radius also remains the same. The magnetic measurements support the view put forward by Kazimierz Jablczynski (*Rocz. Chem.*, 1923, 18, 883, 91) and Abonnenc (*loc. cit.*) that the ionic dimensions are the same in different states as against that of Scott (*loc. cit.*) who is of the opinion that the ionic radius of rubidium is different in different states. The ionic value for the radius of rubidium in the saturated solution is 1.37 while in the dilute solution it is 2.02×10^{-8} cm.

The physical and chemical properties of the rubidium salts, such as solubility, viscosity and refractive index, are in favour of the above mentioned view, namely, the radius of rubidium ion does not change in different states. Rubidium does not form any complexes such as hydrates which would have been responsible to some extent for changing the ionic radius and thereby the ionic diamagnetism of rubidium.

In Table VI the experimental as well as theoretical ionic diamagnetic values of rubidium found by various authors are tabulated.

TABLE VI.

*Ionic diamagnetic values.**Theoretical.*

Pauling.	Stoner.	Slater.	Angus.
35.0.	30.12	25.8	24.08

Experimental.

Pascal,	Ikenmeyer.	Kido.	Abonnenc.	Present authors.
27.2	31.3	27.2	25.0	26.93

These values refer to $-\chi \times 10^6$.

The ionic values obtained closely correspond with the values obtained by Pascal (*loc. cit.*) and Kido (*loc. cit.*). Temperature has practically no influence on the diamagnetism of the rubidium salt.

UNIVERSITY CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY OF THE PUNJAB, LAHORE.

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